

Infrared thermography coupled with deep learning for fast and reliable predictive monitoring of lubricating oils in dual-use heavy-duty vehicles

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ABSTRACT

The reliable evaluation of lubricating oil condition is critical for ensuring the safety and operational efficiency of heavy-duty equipment in both civilian and defense sectors. Conventional laboratory-based physicochemical analyses, although effective, are inherently time-consuming and do not enable real-time diagnostics or on-site decision-making. In this work, we introduce an innovative approach that leverages infrared thermography coupled with deep learning to achieve rapid, non-destructive, and fully automated classification of lubricating oil samples as either “compliant” (fit for use) or “non-compliant” (unfit for use). The study focuses on two reference lubricants (O-1178 (5W30), gearbox oil and O-1236 (15W40), engine oil) widely deployed in military vehicles, with ground-truth class labels established via standardized laboratory protocols. A comprehensive dataset of over 10,000 thermographic images was generated through controlled cooling cycles, providing the foundation for model development. After comparative analysis of several state-of-the-art convolutional neural network architectures, ResNet-34 and ResNet-50 were selected for their superior performance. The models, trained and validated on stratified and balanced datasets, consistently achieved classification accuracies above 99 %, with the ResNet-34 model delivering 100 % sensitivity and specificity for the detection of non-compliant samples in both oil types. Complementary metrics, including ROC/AUC (≈ 1.0) and F1-scores near unity, together with stable training-validation loss convergence, confirmed that the classifiers operated in a saturated performance regime with robust generalization. Interpretation with Grad-CAM heatmaps revealed that the model's decisions are grounded in physically meaningful thermal micropatterns directly linked to lubricant degradation. This strategy not only minimizes unnecessary oil changes and associated environmental impact, but also elevates predictive maintenance capabilities by enabling immediate, reliable diagnostics in dual-use (civil and military) settings. The proposed methodology establishes a robust and versatile framework for advanced lubricant condition monitoring, readily adaptable to other industrial fluids and diverse operational scenarios requiring rapid, on-site assessment. Future work will extend this framework to additional lubricant types and broader real-world conditions to further consolidate these findings.

1. Introduction

Lubrication systems are fundamental to the safety and performance of engines. It has been demonstrated that the safety and performance of diesel engines, gasoline engines, and wind turbines critically depend on the quality of the lubricating oil [1]. Consequently, continuous monitoring of lubricant condition is vital to maximize the reliability and

availability of heavy vehicles in both civil and military applications. In the military context, for example, main battle tanks demand high operational availability to ensure mission success. Several official documents and guidelines have identified rapid and reliable lubricant assessment as a key element in modern defense maintenance strategies [2,3]. In this scenario, condition-based maintenance (CBM) is essential: lubricant condition monitoring (LCM) acts as an early warning system

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and a diagnostic tool for machinery failures [2–5]. Thus, advanced tools capable of real-time evaluation of oil usability increase vehicle availability, prevent unexpected downtime, and extend lubricant service life. Furthermore, postponing unnecessary oil changes saves resources and reduces the generation of hazardous waste, supporting environmental objectives. As highlighted by Wakiru et al. (2018), lubricant analysis provides detailed information on both the condition of the machine and the oil itself, making it an essential component of CBM programs [4].

In recent years, various techniques have been proposed to assess lubricating oil condition. Traditionally, oil analysis includes physicochemical tests (such as viscosity, acid number, water and wear metal contents) and elemental analysis, whose results are interpreted using statistical or artificial intelligence models. For instance, Wakiru et al. (2018) classified LCM tests into categories such as physicochemical, elemental, or contaminant analysis, and indicated that the resulting data can be processed using statistical approaches, knowledge-based models, or AI techniques [4]. Within this framework, neural networks have been used to classify oil condition. Rodrigues et al. (2020) described a neural network model, combined with Principal Component Analysis (PCA), capable of automatically determining the condition of engine oil [1]. This model enabled identification of the most influential variables for optimal oil change timing and showed that in many cases maintenance intervals can be safely extended, avoiding premature oil changes [4]. More recently, some studies have combined thermography with deep learning for mechanical fault diagnosis. Resendiz-Ochoa et al. (2024) used thermographic images of engines and gearboxes together with a basic convolutional neural network, achieving an accuracy of approximately 98.5 % in fault identification [6]. These advances demonstrate that AI- and thermography-based techniques can extract meaningful patterns to assess mechanical system health. However, these studies have focused on detecting component faults (such as broken bars, damaged bearings, or gear wear) and have not been directly applied to the analysis of lubricant condition.

Despite these developments, conventional tools have significant limitations. Traditional oil analysis methods usually require sample extraction and laboratory testing, resulting in delays in detection and high logistical costs. Moreover, current online sensors (such as viscosity or wear particle meters) typically measure only a single property, failing to provide a comprehensive view of lubricant condition. In contrast, infrared thermography is an extremely rapid, non-destructive technique: it enables real-time inspection of large areas and provides intuitive results instantly [7]. By applying a thermal stimulus and recording the cooling process, thermography generates a thermal profile that reflects fluid properties without the need for contact. These features make thermography an attractive alternative for rapid lubricant monitoring, overcoming the temporal limitations of classical methods. As confirmed by several studies, the use of infrared cameras combined with AI can detect mechanical defects within seconds and with high reliability [6,7].

In this context, the approach proposed in this work directly addresses these gaps. In this study, the term “lubricating oil” refers to oils used in both engines and gearboxes. Although part of the cited literature focuses primarily on engine applications, the methodology developed here was conceived from the outset to be applicable to both lubrication systems. We introduce a system based on thermographic analysis of lubricating oil during cooling after thermal excitation. From the series of captured infrared images, the cooling profile, observable as a color change in the fluid, can be constructed, which varies according to the degree of oil degradation. To process these images, we employ two deep neural network models based on the ResNet architecture (ResNet34 and ResNet50), both with and without pretraining. These models learn to identify subtle patterns in the thermal profile that distinguish compliant (fit-for-service) oils from non-compliant (degraded) ones. The classification is performed within seconds, enabling immediate diagnostics without the need for laborious laboratory analysis. Thanks to the capacity of deep networks, the accuracy in determining oil compliance is excellent, with a very low rate of misclassification. While infrared

thermography has proven effective in mechanical fault diagnosis, its direct application to the analysis of lubricating oil condition (especially using deep learning) has scarcely been explored in the literature, with rare exceptions focused on spectroscopy and not on thermographic images [8,9].

In summary, the proposed approach fully meets the intended objectives. Firstly, it enhances the operational availability of heavy-duty vehicles by reliably preventing failures and unnecessary downtime; by accurately identifying when lubricants remain fit for service, oil changes can be postponed until genuinely required. As noted by Rodrigues et al. (2020), safely extending oil change intervals reduces redundant maintenance interventions and optimizes resource allocation [1]. Secondly, this methodology contributes to environmental protection by minimizing the generation of waste oil and supporting more sustainable maintenance practices. In contrast to previous methods that rely on single-parameter online sensors or indirect proxies such as vibration analysis, our approach provides a comprehensive, real-time evaluation of lubricant condition directly from its thermal response. This not only overcomes the limitations of existing technologies but also offers deeper physicochemical insight into oil degradation processes.

The objective of this work is to develop these two intelligent models (ResNet34 and ResNet50, with and without transfer learning) capable of automatically classifying the compliance of engine and gearbox lubricants based on thermographic images acquired during the cooling process, thus overcoming the limitations of current methodologies and responding to the urgent need for efficient predictive maintenance in both civil and military applications.

2. Materials and methods

This section describes the materials, equipment, and methodologies employed to classify the condition of military lubricants using infrared thermography and convolutional neural networks. The objective is to distinguish lubricants as either “compliant” (fit for use) or “non-compliant” (unfit for use) based on thermographic images, following a reproducible and rigorous approach to predictive diagnostics.

2.1. Materials and equipment

This subsection details the materials and experimental resources used in this study, including the selected lubricants and the techniques and equipment employed for their characterization and analysis. First, the lubricating oils were chosen for their operational relevance in heavy military vehicles, and the procedures for representative sample collection and preparation are described. Next, the physicochemical analysis methods used for oil classification are explained, based on critical parameters defined by specific standards, establishing the basis for subsequent training of artificial intelligence models. This section also provides a technical description of the thermographic instrumentation used for infrared image acquisition, as well as the computational resources and development environment used for data processing and modeling. All procedures ensure the traceability, reproducibility, and methodological rigor necessary to validate the results and facilitate the application of this methodology in real-world environments.

- **Analyzed Lubricants:** Two types of lubricating oils, both of strategic importance for heavy military vehicles of the Spanish Army (Ejército de Tierra), were analyzed in this study. These lubricants were selected for their widespread use and logistical relevance in operational settings [10]: (1) a multigrade mineral oil 15W40 (NATO code O-1236), mainly used for diesel engine lubrication in combat vehicles, and (2) a multigrade synthetic oil 5W30 (NATO code O-1178), used in transmission systems and gearboxes. Used oil samples were collected directly from operational vehicles (primarily engines and transmissions of Leopard 2E main battle tanks) following strict standardized protocols for cold sampling, homogenization, and

documentation to ensure representativeness and traceability [11]. In total, the analyzed lubricants were sourced from 45 different engines and gearboxes, providing adequate diversity and robustness to the experimental dataset. For each physical sample, three independent replicates were performed for both sampling and thermographic analysis, increasing the statistical reliability of the results obtained.

- Physicochemical Characterization and Classification:** Each sample underwent laboratory analysis according to ASTM standards to determine its condition. The properties evaluated included kinematic viscosity (at 40 °C and 100 °C, ASTM D445), viscosity index (ASTM D2270), acid number (TAN, ASTM D664), total base number (TBN, ASTM D2896), flash point (ASTM D92/D93), water content (ASTM D6304), carbon residue (ASTM D7686), and metals by rotating disc electrode atomic emission spectroscopy (RDE-AES, ASTM D6595). Each parameter provides key information: viscosity ensures proper lubrication; TAN and TBN reflect chemical degradation; water and carbon residue indicate contamination; and metals reveal internal component wear. Since there are no universal criteria for defining the compliance of used oil, the Spanish Army (Ejército de Tierra) establishes internal limits for these properties through specific technical regulations. According to these guidelines, each sample was classified as “compliant” or “non-compliant” depending on whether its physicochemical values were within acceptable ranges. This binary labeling served to construct the image database with reference categories essential for the supervised training of deep learning models. It is noteworthy that these analyses were performed in accordance with best practices for used oil management, in line with current legislation that prioritizes the efficient regeneration and recycling of lubricants [12,13].
- Thermographic Imaging Equipment:** A Optris Xi 410 thermographic camera (Optris GmbH, Germany) was used for thermal image acquisition. This device captures long-wave infrared radiation (spectral range 7.5–13 μm) and produces images with a resolution of 384 × 240 pixels at a rate of up to 30 Hz. The camera offers a measurement accuracy of ±2 °C (or ±2 % of the reading) and a thermal sensitivity (NETD) of approximately 80 mK at 30 °C, enabling the detection of subtle temperature differences on the surface of the samples. In addition, specific Optris software was used for thermal recording and calibration, ensuring precise mapping of surface temperatures.
- Computational Resources:** Processing and analysis of thermographic images were carried out in a Python (version 3.8) environment using Jupyter Notebook. The neural network models were implemented and trained using the Fastai library (version 2.x) on PyTorch, leveraging its deep learning utilities. Training experiments were performed on a workstation running Ubuntu 22.04 LTS with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU (11 GB), which enabled efficient network training. All software and hardware configurations were documented to ensure the reproducibility of the method.

2.2. Thermographic method

Infrared thermography is based on measuring the thermal radiation emitted by objects and translating it into temperature images, revealing variations associated with material composition. Infrared radiation spans wavelengths from approximately 0.76 μm–15 μm, extending beyond the visible spectrum. This technique has been successfully used to identify compositional anomalies in various fields, for example, in detecting adulterants in food products by exploiting the fact that chemical formulation differences manifest as distinctive thermal patterns during heating or cooling processes. Previous studies have demonstrated that thermography, combined with artificial intelligence analysis, can rapidly and non-invasively distinguish contaminants or degradation in complex matrices [14].

In this study, infrared thermography was employed to assess the condition of lubricating oils based on their thermal behavior. Each

sample, after thorough homogenization, was heated in a controlled manner to an initial temperature of approximately 50 °C, ensuring uniform thermal distribution throughout the liquid mass. The initial temperature of approximately 50 °C was not measured by the infrared camera. Instead, it was verified using an external calibrated thermocouple in direct contact with the oil prior to each cooling experiment. The Optris Xi 410 was therefore used only to record relative thermal emission patterns during cooling, not to measure absolute temperature, and was operated with a fixed emissivity value ($\epsilon = 0.95$), appropriate for hydrocarbon-based oils in the LWIR band. Immediately thereafter, the sample was allowed to cool freely in a controlled environment while sequences of thermographic images were recorded using the Optris Xi 410 camera. This cooling process, similar to that described by Hernansanz-Luque et al. in studies on food samples, enables the capture of differences in heat dissipation between healthy and degraded oils [15].

It is important to clarify that the Optris Xi 410 used in this study operates strictly in the long-wave infrared (LWIR) band, with a detection range of 7.5–13 μm. Both lubricants (O-1178 and O-1236) and the cuvette material are optically opaque in this spectral region, due to the strong infrared absorption of hydrocarbons in the LWIR band. As a result, the camera records only the thermal emission from the oil surface, modulated by its emissivity, and no transmitted or internal radiation contributes to the measured signal.

For each thermographic experiment, a fixed oil volume of 3 mL was used. The oil was placed in a transparent square cuvette (1 cm internal width × 4 cm height), filled to approximately three quarters of its total height. This cuvette geometry ensured a stable optical path and minimized thermal artifacts associated with container thickness or curvature. During acquisition, the sample was positioned in front of the Optris Xi 410 thermographic camera, maintaining a perpendicular orientation to ensure full-field thermal capture of the oil column. In addition, the camera was positioned vertically with a 90° pitch, ensuring that the optical axis was strictly perpendicular to the surface of the cuvette. The detector pixel pitch (17 μm) has also been included for completeness, as provided in the manufacturer's technical specifications. This configuration minimizes angular emissivity effects and guarantees uniform thermal capture across the entire oil column. All experiments used the same cuvette geometry and fixed sample volume to guarantee thermal comparability.

An illustrative diagram of the experimental setup, including the cuvette, the thermographic camera, and representative thermograms obtained during cooling, has been incorporated as Fig. 1 to facilitate reproducibility.

Experimental analysis determined that the optimal temperature range for comparison was approximately 55 to 30 °C, as the most distinctive cooling gradients between compliant and non-compliant samples were observed within this interval. This range coincides with the largest changes in viscosity and thermal conductivity of the evaluated oils, thus maximizing the method's sensitivity to degradation. Thermographic image sequences (videos) were captured at a frequency of 30 Hz during the cooling process, generating a broad and representative dataset for subsequent analysis using deep learning techniques.

In each experiment, the thermographic acquisition lasted between 180 and 200 s, covering the full cooling profile relevant for classification. For each of the 45 engines and 45 gearboxes included in the study, between 8 and 11 oil samples were collected, resulting in a total of 855 individual samples across both lubricant types (O-1178 and O-1236). Each thermographic measurement (i.e., each complete acquisition sequence) was performed in triplicate to identify potential anomalies or acquisition artifacts. When the three repetitions were consistent, the second measurement was selected as the definitive one for analysis. Following this protocol, a total of 2565 thermographic experiments were conducted. From each full acquisition sequence, between 9 and 14 representative thermographic frames were extracted, evenly distributed across the entire cooling process.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the thermographic acquisition setup. The cuvette (1 × 1 × 4 cm, 3 mL) containing lubricant O-1178 or O-1236 is positioned 21 cm from the Optrix Xi 410 LWIR camera, oriented perpendicularly at 90°. All measurements were conducted in an isolated enclosure under controlled environmental conditions (22 °C, 40–50 % RH). From each cooling sequence, 9–14 thermographic frames (30 Hz) were extracted and subsequently used as input for the ResNet-based classification models distinguishing between compliant and non-compliant samples.

All thermographic measurements were conducted under strictly controlled environmental conditions to minimize any external variability. Laboratory ambient temperature was maintained at 22 ± 1 °C and relative humidity between 40 and 50 % using a climate control system, thus avoiding fluctuations that could affect the thermal emission of the samples. Experiments were carried out in an isolated enclosure, free from air currents and external heat sources, so that only the infrared emission from the samples contributed to the recorded images.

The distance between the thermographic camera and the cuvette was fixed at 21 cm. At this short observation distance, the effect of ambient humidity (40–50 %) on infrared transmission in the LWIR band is negligible, as the water-vapour absorption path is extremely small. Consequently, atmospheric attenuation does not introduce measurable errors in the recorded thermal emission.

The camera was mounted on a tripod, maintaining a fixed distance from the sample container and ensuring the entire surface of the oil was within the field of view. Additionally, it was confirmed that the container used did not introduce reflections or artifacts in the thermographic readings, and all containers were covered during the experimental process to avoid condensation, especially in oils with higher water content.

All recordings were made under identical geometric and temporal conditions, starting the acquisition only once the sample reached the established initial temperature. Maintaining all experimental degrees of freedom (initial temperature, camera distance and angle, sample volume, among others) constant was crucial to ensure that the differences observed in the cooling curves were attributable exclusively to the state of the lubricant (composition and degradation) and not to external factors. Should these initial conditions vary in future experiments, it will be necessary to recalibrate or retrain the classification model to maintain its effectiveness.

The thermographic images obtained from each cooling sequence were stored for further analysis. Prior to the modeling stage, a data processing step was applied to extract from the videos those frames or features that highlighted characteristic thermal patterns of each sample class. For example, temperature difference maps or temporal cooling curves could be calculated for each sample, although in this work the main strategy was to feed the individual images directly into a neural network model capable of autonomously learning these patterns. In this way, thermography provides a visually rich dataset that reflects the intrinsic thermal behavior of oils under different quality conditions.

2.3. Convolutional neural networks

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning model specifically designed for image processing, which have proven highly effective in the automatic detection of complex patterns. In a CNN, layers of artificial neurons process visual information hierarchically: the initial layers extract local features (edges, textures, heat spots), while the deeper layers combine these features to identify higher-level structures associated with the classes of interest. Through an

iterative training process, the network adjusts its internal parameters (weights) to minimize classification error, thus learning subtle differences directly from the image data [16]. Given their ability to autonomously detect complex relationships in images, CNNs are ideal for the goal of this work, which is to identify lubricant oil degradation from thermographic signatures without the need to manually define visual indicators.

In this study, a deep CNN based on the ResNet-34 (Residual Network, 34 layers) architecture was implemented to perform binary classification of the thermographic images of lubricants. The ResNet-34 architecture was chosen after considering several state-of-the-art alternatives in computer vision. For example, models such as EfficientNet, known for high efficiency and accuracy in natural images, and MobileNet, optimized for low-power devices [17,18], as well as classical architectures such as VGG16 or DenseNet, were evaluated. However, ResNet-34 offered the best balance between performance and complexity, thanks to its residual structure, which allows deeper networks to be trained without gradient degradation issues. Previous studies have validated the effectiveness of ResNet-34 in detecting thermal anomalies in complex products, showing advantages for distinguishing subtle patterns in infrared images [14]. In the context of oils, where visual differences can be very subtle (e.g., smooth color gradients or slight opacity changes), leveraging a deep residual network is particularly advantageous to achieve high generalization capacity.

The implemented ResNet-34 consists of the following main components:

- **Input layer:** receives each thermographic image as a fixed-size matrix (e.g., 224×224 pixels) and normalizes pixel values to fit the network's input range.
- **Convolutional layers:** apply learned filters to the image to extract relevant local features (edges, textures, regional thermal patterns).
- **ReLU activation layers (Rectified Linear Unit):** introduce non-linearity after each convolution, allowing the modeling of complex relationships in the data.
- **Batch normalization layers:** stabilize the activation distribution in each layer, accelerating training convergence and improving stability.
- **Residual blocks:** distinctive elements of ResNet-34 that incorporate identity shortcuts between layers, facilitating gradient propagation across many layers. These blocks allow for deeper networks to be trained without degradation or stagnation in performance.
- **Pooling layers (downsampling):** reduce the dimensionality of feature maps by aggregating information over regions, increasing computational efficiency while preserving the most important features.
- **Fully connected layer:** integrates the features extracted by the previous layers and transforms them into a final representation suitable for classification.
- **Output layer with Softmax activation:** assigns a probability to each output category; in our case, two probabilities corresponding to

the “compliant” and “non-compliant” classes, determining the network’s prediction.

During model development, two common transfer learning strategies were explored: (1) partial fine-tuning, where most pre-trained layers of ResNet-34 are initially frozen and only the final classifier layers are fully trained; and (2) full fine-tuning, in which all network layers remain trainable, enabling comprehensive adaptation to the specific characteristics of the oil images. Partial fine-tuning requires less data and helps avoid early overfitting by leveraging generic features learned from large datasets (e.g., ImageNet), while full fine-tuning can achieve maximum performance by specializing on our specific dataset. In this work, both approaches were tested to evaluate which provided better classification accuracy for the lubricants.

2.4. Learning algorithm and training process

The neural network training was formulated as a classic supervised learning problem. The error backpropagation algorithm was used in conjunction with a stochastic gradient-based optimizer to adjust the weights of the CNN, minimizing the difference between the network’s predictions and the true sample classifications. Specifically, Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with momentum was employed as the optimizer, and the chosen loss function was cross-entropy loss, which is appropriate for binary classification problems. Careful tuning of the training hyperparameters was performed to achieve rapid and stable convergence. In particular, the optimal learning rate was identified using a stepwise search strategy, which helped avoid local minima and accelerate learning [19,20]. In addition, regularization techniques such as weight normalization and dropout in intermediate layers were incorporated to prevent overfitting and improve the model’s generalization ability. These techniques reduce the model’s excessive reliance on spurious or noisy features in the training data, making the model more robust to new samples.

2.4.1. Dataset preparation

The complete set of thermographic images was systematically organized into a labelled dataset that served as the foundation for training the neural network models. Each image was annotated with its corresponding oil type (O-1178 or O-1236) and compliance status (“compliant” or “non-compliant”), ensuring full traceability between the laboratory reference results and the image data. The images used in this study were extracted frame-by-frame from the visual thermographic video recorded by the Optris Xi 410, reflecting the standard output generated by the camera during acquisition. The preprocessing pipeline was minimal and limited to: (i) conversion of the extracted frames into a consistent colour-space representation; (ii) resizing to 224×224 pixels to comply with the input requirements of the ResNet architectures; and (iii) pixel-value normalization according to ImageNet statistics (zero mean and unit variance per channel). No additional cropping, filtering, smoothing, denoising, contrast enhancement, or artefact-removal operations were applied at any stage. The physical dimensions of the cuvette (1×4 cm) refer exclusively to the real geometry of the experimental setup and do not imply any spatial rescaling of the image data used for training or validation.

To prevent data leakage and ensure the validity of the results, all thermographic images derived from the same physical oil sample (i.e., from the same batch and sampling event) were assigned exclusively to a single subset (training, validation, or test). This strategy eliminated the possibility of the model encountering visually similar images during both training and evaluation phases, thereby providing an unbiased and realistic estimation of predictive performance.

To provide a clear overview of the dataset used in this study and its relevance for the subsequent data preparation stages, we include below a detailed summary of all thermographic images acquired for both lubricants and compliance categories. This quantitative description is

essential to understand the structure of the dataset prior to applying the stratified splitting procedure used for training, validation, and testing of the deep learning models. Accordingly, Table 1 presents the complete distribution of images for oil types O-1178 and O-1236, broken down into compliant and non-compliant classes, forming the basis for the sampling strategy described in the following section.

As shown in Table 1, the total number of thermographic images used in this study amounted to 10,062, distributed between the two selected types of industrial oils. For the gearbox oil (O-1178), 3670 compliant and 3191 non-compliant images were analyzed, totaling 6861 images. For the engine lubricant (O-1236), the dataset comprised 1712 compliant and 1489 non-compliant images, reaching a total of 3201 images. In total, the “compliant” group comprised 5382 images, while the “non-compliant” group included 4680 images.

2.4.2. Data splitting

To train and objectively evaluate the model, the image set was divided into three independent subsets using stratified sampling: (a) Training set (approximately 70 % of the images), used to adjust the network weights during learning; (b) Validation set (approximately 20 %), used to monitor model performance during training, fine-tune hyperparameters, and detect potential overfitting; and (c) Blind test set (approximately 10 %), reserved entirely for the final assessment of the model’s true predictive ability on unseen data. Stratified selection ensured that each subset preserved the same proportion of classes (“compliant”/“non-compliant”) and oil types as in the total dataset. Furthermore, care was taken to prevent images from the same physical sample (i.e., the same batch of lubricating oil) from appearing in more than one subset, thus avoiding the risk of the model benefiting from unique sample-specific patterns during validation.

It is important to highlight that no data augmentation techniques were applied during preprocessing in this study. Given that all images were acquired under highly controlled and standardized conditions, we considered that artificial transformations could introduce visual artifacts that are unrealistic or not representative of the actual samples. This consideration is especially relevant due to the semi-transparent nature and subtle thermal contrasts of the lubricating oils analyzed. Instead, the model relied on the intrinsic variability present in the original dataset, which included samples with different degrees of degradation and two types of oils, thus ensuring adequate generalization capability. Although data augmentation is commonly used to improve the generalization of deep learning models, in our case, the high degree of experimental control and the physical homogeneity of the samples made such artificial modifications unnecessary and potentially detrimental to the interpretability of the results. The validity of this decision is supported by the excellent accuracy and reproducibility achieved in the model’s performance.

2.4.3. Training and validation procedure

With the data prepared and split, the ResNet-34 architecture was trained. During each iteration (epoch), the model processed batches of training images (batch size = 32), updating its parameters via SGD according to the computed error gradient. The optimal learning rate, determined through stepwise search, was employed, and regularization techniques and early stopping were applied to avoid overfitting: if validation performance ceased to improve, training was halted early.

Table 1
Distribution of the number of thermographic images used for training and validating the classification models, broken down by oil type (O-1178 and O-1236) and state (compliant/non-compliant).

Oil Type	Compliant Images	Non-compliant images	Total images
O-1178	3670	3191	6861
O-1236	1712	1489	3201
Total	5382	4680	10,062

Training typically converged in fewer than 20 epochs, at which point the loss function stabilized and accuracy ceased to increase significantly. After training, the model was evaluated on the reserved, completely blind test set, thus providing a realistic estimate of its generalization capability to unseen images simulating real-world conditions.

To strengthen the robustness of the results and rule out potential biases due to random data splitting, an additional stratified k-fold cross-validation procedure ($k = 5$) was implemented. The model was trained and evaluated five times, rotating the validation and test subsets, and key metrics' means and standard deviations were calculated. Furthermore, to guarantee result robustness, each training run was repeated with different random seeds, minimizing the effect of potential "lucky splits."

The final model's performance was evaluated using not only overall accuracy, but also confusion matrices and class-specific metrics, for both non-compliant sample detection (critical for predictive maintenance) and compliant samples. The training process implemented, combined with the robust ResNet-34 architecture and the strict experimental controls described, resulted in an autonomous diagnostic system capable of evaluating lubricant condition from thermographic images with high reliability and reproducibility.

3. Results and discussion

The most relevant results of the study are presented below, with particular emphasis on the thermographic behavior of the oils, the quality of the dataset, and the performance of the developed models. The objective is to clearly and rigorously demonstrate the scope, robustness, and technical implications of the proposed methodology in the context of predictive diagnostics for lubricants.

3.1. Interpretation of Grad-CAM heatmaps and gradient distribution: relevance in automatic classification

The quality, diversity, and representativeness of the thermographic images used form the essential foundation for the development and validation of the proposed mathematical models. To ensure the robustness of the results, a rigorous selection and classification of the samples was carried out, along with an exhaustive analysis of the thermal and gradient patterns present in the images.

3.1.1. Gradient distribution: representativeness and quality of the images

Histograms of gradient magnitude (GRAD-MAD) for each lubricant type are shown in Fig. 2 [21]. These histograms reflect the frequency of thermal transitions within each analyzed image. In both cases, a very high frequency of low gradients is observed, indicating that the vast majority of images exhibit homogeneous thermal morphology, with no anomalies or unexpected artifacts.

To visually illustrate this distribution and facilitate understanding of

Fig. 2. GRAD-MAD gradient distributions for thermographic images of O-1178 oil (a) and O-1236 oil (b).

the actual appearance of the images in the database, Fig. 3 presents representative examples of thermographic images from both O-1178 and O-1236. Each block shows, in the first row, three images selected with the lowest gradient values ($G = 0$); these are samples that exhibit a homogeneous and stable thermal pattern, characteristic of well-represented and physically reliable oils. The second row includes images with the highest gradient values detected in the dataset (high G values), considered anomalous or non-representative. The corresponding gradient value (G) is indicated above each image.

As can be seen, the images with low gradients exhibit smooth transitions between thermal zones, with no spots or abrupt changes, reflecting the homogeneity and overall quality of the database. In contrast, the images with high gradients display greater fluctuations, irregular patterns, or areas of intense thermal variability, associated with anomalous situations, artifacts, or acquisition issues, Fig. 2.

Quantitatively, only 61 images in the case of O-1178 and 31 in the case of O-1236 showed high gradients that could be considered atypical

Fig. 3. Examples of thermographic front-view images included in the database for O-1178 oil (left) and O-1236 oil (right). Each rectangular panel corresponds to the frontal surface of the cuvette, which has an internal cross-section of $1 \text{ cm} \times 4 \text{ cm}$. In each group, the top row shows images with the lowest gradient values ($G = 0$), representing homogeneous and highly representative thermal states. The bottom row shows images with the highest detected gradient values (high G), corresponding to atypical or non-representative thermal patterns. The numerical gradient value (G) is indicated above each image.

or non-representative. This represents less than 1 % of the total images for each group, which ensures the extremely high quality and representativeness of the dataset used for model training and validation. The low incidence of discarded images confirms that the database is suitable for modeling the physicochemical reality of the oils and avoids bias due to defective or uncontrolled data.

The predominance of low gradients also suggests that most samples do not exhibit artifacts or alterations that could interfere with automatic diagnosis. This is especially relevant in applied thermography studies, where the quality and homogeneity of the dataset directly influence the robustness of the model and the reliability of the results [22].

3.1.2. Grad-CAM heatmaps: critical regions for model decision-making

Before analysing the heatmaps, it is important to introduce the Grad-CAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping) method employed in this study. Grad-CAM is an explainability technique that highlights the image regions most influential for a convolutional neural network's prediction, as originally proposed by Selvaraju et al. (2017) [23]. The method computes the gradients of the predicted class score with respect to the feature maps of the last convolutional layer, averages these gradients to obtain importance weights, and combines them to generate a class-discriminative localization map. The improved formulation and its robustness for model interpretability were later extended in Selvaraju et al. (2020) [24]. When this localization map is upsampled and overlaid on the original thermographic image, it reveals the spatial areas that contribute most strongly to the classification decision. In the context of lubricant diagnostics, Grad-CAM enables the identification of subtle thermal micro-patterns associated with physicochemical degradation, providing transparency and physical interpretability to the deep learning model.

The interpretation and analysis of heatmaps generated by the Grad-CAM technique is essential to understand the basis and high effectiveness of the mathematical model used for classifying lubricating oils from thermographic images [21,23]. As shown in Fig. 4, the heatmaps do not represent a direct thermographic image, but rather the relative importance of each region of the image for the model's classification decision.

In both oils, O-1178 and O-1236, the heatmaps show a spatially heterogeneous distribution of importance assigned by the model to different regions of the image. Warm colors (red, yellow, orange) indicate regions where the model detects key features that decisively contribute to discriminating between “compliant” and “non-compliant” states. Cool colors (blue, green), on the other hand, correspond to areas with very low or negligible relevance for prediction.

This pattern reveals that the model does not base its decision on the global image or random artifacts, but rather learns to focus on micro-patterns or localized thermal anomalies whose presence or absence is strongly correlated with the physicochemical degradation of the lubricant. For example, warm colors may highlight areas where thermal morphology reveals anomalous accumulation of contaminants, micro-heterogeneity due to oxidation, or wear-induced textures, features that would be imperceptible to the human eye but detected by the algorithm. The existence of large areas with cool colors is also significant, as it demonstrates that, for most of the sample surface, there are no major alterations; this contributes to the robustness of the model by reducing the risk of overfitting and decisions based on noise [22–24].

This focusing ability translates into increased explainability of the model: the deep neural network does not operate as a “black box,” but instead transparently identifies and weighs the thermally most relevant regions for automatic diagnosis. In the literature, this type of local importance analysis has been validated for pathology detection in medical images and for industrial quality control, demonstrating that localized “attention” improves both the accuracy and interpretability of artificial intelligence systems [24].

The combination of interpretable heatmaps and controlled gradient distributions provides a double guarantee: on one hand, the model identifies and exploits truly critical regions for classification; on the

Fig. 4. Grad-CAM heatmaps for representative thermographic images of O-1178 oil (left) and O-1236 oil (right). Each heatmap corresponds to the frontal surface of the cuvette, with an internal physical size of 1 cm in width (base) and 4 cm in height.

other, the image quality ensures that predictions are based on physically relevant information rather than artifacts. This approach reinforces confidence in the methodology, providing transparency, robustness, and a solid scientific basis for the entire process of automatic oil analysis using thermography and deep learning [23,24].

3.2. Characterization of the samples used for model training

Proper experimental design and sample selection are critical to ensuring the robustness, reliability, and validity of any artificial intelligence-based classification model. In this study, optimisation and validation of the mathematical models were performed using a comprehensive and well-balanced set of thermographic images of lubricating oils, specifically of two industrial types: O-1178 (gearbox oil) and O-1236 (engine lubricant).

All images used to train and validate the models were acquired via infrared thermography, ensuring the capture of surface temperature distribution and the characteristic thermal patterns of each sample under controlled conditions. This approach leverages the sensitivity of thermography to physicochemical and structural changes in lubricants, as analyzed in detail in subsequent sections.

Sample classification into the “compliant” and “non-compliant” groups was performed in advance using standard physicochemical analyses, thus ensuring correspondence between the image label and the actual state of the lubricant. This procedure provides the necessary scientific basis for evaluating the diagnostic capability of the models, minimizing bias and guaranteeing the relevance of the results for real-world predictive maintenance and quality control applications, Table 1.

It is noteworthy that the database displays a suitable balance between both groups, with only 15 % more images classified as

“compliant” compared to “non-compliant.” This slight imbalance is intentional and partially reflects the expected distribution in industrial applications, where maintenance systems aim to anticipate and primarily detect non-compliant cases, although most sampled lubricants tend to be within specification.

The diversity and representativeness of the samples are ensured both by the total number of images and by the coverage of different types of industrial lubricants and their respective degradation mechanisms. This sampling strategy allows not only the evaluation of model accuracy under controlled conditions but also its generalization capability across different operational contexts.

Proper stratification and accurate labeling of the samples therefore constitute the basis for all subsequent calculations and analyses regarding performance, robustness, and the physicochemical foundations of the classification, enabling the interpretation of results with full guarantees of representativeness and scientific validity.

3.3. Evaluation and selection of deep learning models for thermographic image classification

The development of a robust and reliable model for the automatic classification of thermographic images of lubricating oils required the systematic exploration of various CNN architectures, ultimately selecting ResNet-34 and ResNet-50 based on an exhaustive comparative analysis of performance, efficiency, and generalization ability.

In the initial phase, several widely recognized reference architectures in computer vision were tested. Among them were EfficientNet, known for optimizing the trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency by scaling model size and depth in a compound manner to maximize performance with limited resources [17]. MobileNet was also evaluated, a lightweight architecture designed for embedded or low-power devices, which uses depthwise separable convolutions to significantly reduce the number of parameters [18]. Other tested options included VGG16 and DenseNet, classical models with proven effectiveness in general image classification but with limitations in terms of efficiency or risk of overfitting when applied to datasets with subtle differences [24].

During testing, both EfficientNet and MobileNet performed well on standard classification tasks but struggled to capture the complexity of thermal patterns and subtle variations characteristic of infrared images of industrial oils. VGG16 and DenseNet, although achieving acceptable accuracy rates, were more prone to overfitting, requiring greater regularization and showing less stability in the identification of localized thermal anomalies. These limitations were evident in cross-validation metrics, with lower sensitivity and specificity than those obtained with the residual architectures.

In this context, ResNet-34 emerged as the model with the best balance between complexity, feature extraction capacity, and robustness against noisy data or high intra-class variability. The key to its performance lies in the incorporation of residual (skip) connections, which facilitate the training of deep networks by mitigating the vanishing gradient problem, allowing the network to learn both global and local patterns in the images [25]. This is critical for lubricant oil analysis, where the distinction between compliant and non-compliant samples may depend on micro-thermal patterns that are difficult to detect with conventional architectures. Recent studies have shown that ResNet-34 excels in detecting thermal anomalies and in industrial applications based on infrared images, justifying its suitability in this domain.

Simultaneously, ResNet-50 was included in the final comparative analysis due to its greater depth and capacity to model complex nonlinear relationships. ResNet-50 has been widely used in advanced classification tasks and shows improvements in capturing fine details, at the cost of higher computational requirements [25]. The inclusion of both variants allowed for a solid benchmarking framework, evaluating both extreme sensitivity (the ability to avoid missing defective samples) and specificity and efficiency.

In summary, the final selection of ResNet-34 and ResNet-50 as reference architectures responds to empirical performance criteria as well as considerations of robustness and explainability, supported by recent literature in computer vision applied to industry and by the experimental evidence obtained in this work. This strategy ensures maximum reliability and transferability of the results, meeting the highest standards of high-impact scientific publications.

3.4. Classification performance for O-1178 lubricant (gearbox oil)

To evaluate and compare the performance of the developed models, confusion matrices corresponding to the ResNet-34 and ResNet-50 architectures were analyzed for the thermographic diagnosis of O-1178 oil images. The results are presented below for both partial optimisation (last layers fine-tuned) and full optimisation (all network parameters fine-tuned), allowing for identification of the most suitable architecture and configuration for the proposed industrial application.

Table 2 summarises the confusion matrices obtained for O-1178 oil using the two reference CNN architectures, ResNet-34 and ResNet-50, evaluated under partial optimisation mode (fine-tuning of the last layers) and full optimisation mode (fine-tuning of all network parameters). In addition to the confusion matrices, the table now includes complementary performance metrics (Precision, Recall, and F1-score) for the Compliant (positive) class. These additional metrics provide a more complete quantitative characterisation of the models' behaviour and reinforce the robustness observed in the classification results. As shown, both architectures achieved very high discriminative performance, with minimal false negatives and false positives, confirming the suitability of the proposed approach for industrial-grade diagnostic applications.

From a practical standpoint and given the importance of minimizing the possibility of misclassifying a non-compliant sample as compliant, the performance of the fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 model is particularly noteworthy. This model was the only one to achieve error-free classification for the “non-compliant” class, correctly identifying all 646 NC samples without a single false negative, while also maintaining excellent performance for the compliant class. In contrast, the full version of ResNet-50, though also outstanding, presented six false negatives in the NC class, which could compromise the system's reliability in contexts where safety or predictive maintenance are critical. Consequently, the selection of fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 as the definitive model addresses the need to ensure maximum sensitivity and specificity for the “non-compliant” class, eliminating the risk of accepting defective samples as valid, an essential requirement for the diagnosis of industrial oils in highly demanding environments.

The fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 model achieved outstanding performance in the classification of O-1178 lubricant samples, as reflected in the confusion matrix in Table 2. Out of 574 actual Compliant (C) images, 549 were correctly identified, while only 25 ($\approx 2.3\%$) were misclassified as Non-Compliant (NC). For the NC class, the model reached perfect detection (646/646), yielding no false negatives, a critical requirement in maintenance applications. This behaviour is further supported by the complementary performance metrics included in Table 2. Precision, Recall, and F1-score for the Compliant class are all close to unity, confirming both the low incidence of false alarms and the high sensitivity in detecting in-specification samples. Positive predictive values remain high for both classes, with predictions of NC being correct in 100 % of cases and predictions of C in 97.9 % of cases. Collectively, these results demonstrate an excellent balance between sensitivity and specificity, with virtually negligible misclassification. The model therefore provides a highly reliable and robust diagnostic tool for industrial environments where accurate distinction between compliant and non-compliant oils is essential.

To complement the confusion matrices and provide additional transparency regarding the learning dynamics of the models, Fig. 5 presents the training-validation loss curves for all architectures

Fig. 6. ROC curves and AUC values for the O-1178 lubricant. Panels correspond to: (a) ResNet-34 (partial fine-tuning), (b) ResNet-34 (full fine-tuning), (c) ResNet-50 (partial fine-tuning), (d) ResNet-50 (full fine-tuning).

provides strong statistical evidence of the discriminative capability and generalisation strength of the proposed thermography-based classification approach.

Beyond the global AUC values, a closer inspection of the ROC curves in Fig. 6 provides additional insight into the behaviour of each model. For ResNet-34, both the partial and full fine-tuning configurations (panels (a) and (b)) exhibit curves that remain very close to the upper-left corner of the plot, achieving true positive rates above 0.99 with false positive rates well below 0.01 for a wide range of thresholds. This indicates that, in practical terms, the model can simultaneously maintain almost perfect detection of compliant samples and an extremely low rate of false alarms. In contrast, the ResNet-50 partial model (panel (c)) shows a more gradual rise in TPR as the threshold is relaxed, with an AUC of 0.892, revealing a stronger dependence on the chosen operating point. The ResNet-50 full configuration (panel (d)) exhibits intermediate behaviour, with a high AUC (0.971) but still slightly less stable than ResNet-34 across the entire threshold range.

These ROC characteristics provide information that cannot be obtained from the confusion matrices or loss curves alone, which describe performance at a single decision threshold and at the training stage, respectively. The ROC analysis confirms that there are no hidden regions of poor performance: for all reasonable thresholds, the fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 model in particular maintains an excellent balance between sensitivity and specificity, which justifies its selection as the preferred configuration for industrial deployment. Moreover, the ability of the ROC curves to summarise the ranking quality of the models further supports the robustness and generalisation capability of the proposed thermographic diagnostic approach for O-1178 gearbox oil.

During training, not only was high accuracy achieved, but the loss

function also showed stable convergence (not shown here) and an absence of significant overfitting: internal validation performance was practically identical to that of training. This indicates that the model generalizes well for this O-1178 oil dataset. Additionally, as shown in previous sections, visual interpretation of classification was performed using Grad-CAM techniques. These visualizations confirmed that the neural network focuses its attention on distinctive features of the thermographic images when making classification decisions. In summary, for O-1178 lubricant, the model reliably identified these subtle variations in the images, achieving performance metrics consistent with an industrial-level classification system.

It is worth noting that, although a few isolated misclassifications were identified, detailed analysis of these samples did not reveal any common pattern or recurring trend that could be linked to a specific cause. This lack of systematic error suggests that the model maintains robust and generalizable behavior in the face of the diversity present in the dataset used.

3.5. Classification performance for O-1236 lubricant (engine oil)

For the case of O-1236 engine oil, a detailed evaluation was conducted to validate the classification models' ability to accurately identify both compliant and non-compliant samples of this specific lubricant. The following section presents the confusion matrices obtained for the different configurations of ResNet-34 and ResNet-50, enabling an objective comparison of each model's performance and supporting the selection of the optimal architecture for this application.

Table 3 presents the confusion matrices obtained for O-1236 oil together with the corresponding Precision, Recall, and F1-score values

Table 3

Confusion matrices and performance metrics for the classification of O-1236 (engine oil) images in the last model iteration. Results are shown for ResNet-34 and ResNet-50 under partial optimisation and full optimisation configurations. The confusion matrices indicate the number of samples classified into “Compliant” (C) and “Non-Compliant” (NC). Complementary performance metrics (Precision, Recall and F1-score) computed for the Compliant class (positive class) are included to provide a more rigorous assessment of the models’ discriminative capability.

Resnet 34						Resnet 50					
Partial	C	NC	Full	C	NC	Partial	C	NC	Full	C	NC
C	341	7	C	345	3	C	344	4	C	342	6
NC	0	261	NC	0	261	NC	1	260	NC	2	259
Metrics for Compliant Class (Positive Class)											
Precision	1.000		1.000			0.997		0.994			
Recall	0.980		0.991			0.989		0.983			
F1-score	0.990		0.996			0.993		0.988			

computed for the Compliant (positive) class. As in the previous case, these complementary metrics provide a more rigorous and transparent evaluation of model performance. The results confirm the excellent discriminative capability of both ResNet architectures and highlight the slight performance improvements achieved through full fine-tuning, particularly in reducing misclassification of non-compliant samples.

A detailed analysis highlights the excellent performance of the fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 model, which managed to correctly identify all non-compliant samples (261 out of 261), without any false negatives in this operationally critical class. In contrast, the fully fine-tuned ResNet-50 model, while maintaining very high sensitivity and specificity, presented two false negatives in the NC class and six false positives in the C class, which can pose a risk in applications where classifying a non-compliant sample as compliant is unacceptable. For this reason, and in line with the strictest criteria, the fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 architecture was selected as the most suitable model, as it guarantees the absence of critical errors in the detection of degraded oils, providing maximum reliability for the automatic classification system.

The fully fine-tuned ResNet-34 model also delivered exceptional performance for O-1236 engine oil, as shown in Table 3. Of the 348 Compliant (C) images, 345 were correctly identified, with only 3 misclassified as Non-Compliant (NC). All 261 NC samples were correctly

detected, resulting in perfect sensitivity for the non-compliant class—a critical requirement for avoiding undetected degraded engine oil. These results translate into an overall accuracy of 99.5 %, slightly higher than that obtained for O-1178. The additional metrics included in Table 2—Precision, Recall, and F1-score for the Compliant class—are all above 0.99, confirming both the extremely low false-alarm rate (specificity ≈ 99.5 %) and the model’s ability to detect compliant cases reliably. The precision for compliant predictions reached 99.1 %, while predictions of non-compliant oil were correct in 100 % of cases, yielding exceptionally high predictive values for both classes. Taken together, the confusion matrix and complementary metrics provide strong evidence that the model achieves near-perfect separability between compliant and non-compliant engine-oil samples. These results, consistent with those reported for O-1178, reinforce the robustness and generalisability of the proposed thermographic classification methodology across different lubricant types.

To complement the classification results obtained for the O-1236 lubricant and to provide a more comprehensive view of the learning behaviour of the models, Fig. 7 presents the evolution of the loss function across the 20 training epochs. These plots illustrate how the different ResNet configurations adapt to the characteristic thermal patterns of engine oil and offer valuable insight into the internal

Fig. 7. Evolution of training and validation loss for the O-1236 engine-oil dataset. Circular markers indicate validation loss, and triangular markers indicate training loss. Panels correspond to: (a) ResNet-34 with partial fine-tuning; (b) ResNet-34 with full fine-tuning; (c) ResNet-50 with partial fine-tuning; (d) ResNet-50 with full fine-tuning.

learning dynamics beyond the final confusion matrices. By comparing the four scenarios, partial and full fine-tuning of ResNet-34 and ResNet-50, it is possible to assess the practical effect of fine-tuning depth on model stability and on the extraction of lubricant-specific features during training.

The analysis of the curves in Fig. 7 reveals a learning behavior that differs from that observed for the O-1178 lubricant, reflecting the distinct thermographic properties of engine oil. In the partial fine-tuning configurations (panels (a) and (c)), the reduction in loss is more gradual and exhibits small oscillations during the early epochs, suggesting greater initial variability in capturing the characteristic patterns of O-1236. Conversely, the full fine-tuning configurations (panels (b) and (d)) show a steeper loss decrease during the first training stages, followed by a long stabilization phase at very low values, indicating that the deeper layers rapidly learn the most informative thermal gradients associated with engine-oil degradation. Furthermore, the minimal separation between training and validation curves throughout all epochs indicates consistent learning and the absence of significant discrepancies between seen and unseen data. This learning pattern—defined by rapid convergence and sustained stability—supports the strong classification performance achieved for O-1236, demonstrating that fully fine-tuned architectures leverage the thermal structure of the lubricant more effectively and produce more reliable and robust diagnostic models.

To complement the confusion-matrix analysis and to provide a threshold-independent evaluation of classifier performance, Fig. 8 presents the ROC curves and the corresponding AUC values for all ResNet configurations applied to the O-1236 engine-oil dataset. Overall, the curves reveal a very strong discriminative capacity across all models,

with fully fine-tuned architectures achieving AUC values close to 1.000. ResNet-34 (full) in particular exhibits a nearly ideal ROC shape, maintaining high true-positive rates across the entire range of false-positive rates. Partial fine-tuning also yields robust results, though with slightly reduced AUC values, especially for ResNet-50, indicating a greater sensitivity-specificity trade-off when fewer network layers are updated. These ROC/AUC findings reinforce the conclusions drawn from the confusion matrices and show that the classifier preserves excellent ranking ability even under variations of the decision threshold, confirming its reliability for the detection of degraded engine-oil samples.

A closer inspection of the ROC curves in Fig. 8 provides additional insight into the behaviour of the models for O-1236 that cannot be obtained from single-threshold metrics alone. The ResNet-34 configurations (panels (a) and (b)) show curves that hug the upper-left corner of the plot over a wide range of operating points. In the fully fine-tuned case (AUC \approx 0.998), the curve is almost vertical at very low false-positive rates, indicating that the classifier can achieve true-positive rates above 0.99 while keeping the false-positive rate close to zero. This means that, in practical terms, the decision threshold can be shifted within a relatively broad interval without sacrificing either sensitivity or specificity, which is an important property for deployment under varying industrial conditions.

The ResNet-50 models exhibit a slightly different profile. The partial fine-tuning configuration (panel (c), AUC \approx 0.966) has a more gradual ascent, particularly in the low-FPR region, revealing that its performance is more sensitive to the exact choice of decision threshold: small changes in the operating point can have a noticeable impact on the

Fig. 8. ROC curves and AUC values for the O-1236 lubricant. Panels correspond to: (a) ResNet-34 (partial fine-tuning), (b) ResNet-34 (full fine-tuning), (c) ResNet-50 (partial fine-tuning), (d) ResNet-50 (full fine-tuning).

balance between missed detections and false alarms. In contrast, the fully fine-tuned ResNet-50 (panel (d), $AUC \approx 0.996$) largely recovers the near-ideal shape observed for ResNet-34, achieving high true-positive rates even under very restrictive false-positive constraints. Taken together, these ROC characteristics show that the fully fine-tuned models, especially ResNet-34, provide not only excellent accuracy at the nominal threshold, but also robust performance across the whole range of clinically relevant operating points. This threshold-stability aspect, which is not visible from the confusion matrices or F1-scores, is crucial for applications where the acceptable trade-off between missed degraded oils and false alarms may vary from one operational scenario to another.

It is noteworthy that the O-1236 dataset contained approximately half as many samples as O-1178; nevertheless, the model did not show any performance degradation, suggesting that the discriminative features in the engine oil images are particularly strong. Grad-CAM inspection of O-1236 images indicated that the network focuses attention on warmer color patterns. Specifically, it highlighted areas of this tone, characteristic of heavily used engine oil (laden with soot and combustion byproducts), in contrast to the cooler tones of a new or well-maintained lubricant. The model successfully captures these variations, translating physicochemical differences into distinguishable visual features. In summary, the ResNet-34 network demonstrates robust and reliable performance for O-1236, offering early detection of unsuitable oil conditions with accuracy exceeding 99 %.

While a few occasional misclassifications were observed, no systematic patterns or recurring biases were detected, confirming the model's robustness to data variability. Notably, no false negatives occurred in the detection of non-compliant oils, ensuring operational safety. However, the methodology is limited to the tested oil types and conditions, and further validation will be necessary for broader applications.

3.6. Comparative classification: gearbox oil (O-1178) vs. engine oil (O-1236)

Comparison of the classification performance of ResNet-34 models for O-1178 and O-1236 lubricants, using thermographic images as input, reveals that infrared thermography is an extremely effective tool for discriminating between "compliant" and "non-compliant" states of lubricating oils. Both models achieved accuracies above 98 %, demonstrating exceptional robustness and generalization capability regardless of lubricant type. This high effectiveness is especially significant considering that the information extracted does not originate from conventional visual patterns (color, visible opacity, etc.), but from the temperature distribution and surface emissivity captured by infrared cameras, commonly referred to as thermal imagers.

A deeper comparative analysis between the two lubricants reveals relevant differences in how the models learn and interpret their thermographic signatures. For gearbox oil (O-1178), the thermal patterns associated with compliant and non-compliant samples tend to be more homogeneous, resulting in a more gradual reduction of loss and slightly higher variability during the first epochs of training, as reflected in the learning curves. In contrast, engine oil (O-1236) exhibits more pronounced thermal differences due to the presence of combustion byproducts and metallic wear particles originating from engine components, both of which modify the lubricant's thermal conductivity and dissipation behaviour. These factors enable the networks—particularly in the fully fine-tuned configurations—to extract discriminative features more rapidly and to reach lower and more stable loss values. Such differences in the shape and evolution of the curves indicate that each lubricant presents a distinct thermographic complexity, and that the models adapt their internal representations accordingly, despite ultimately achieving similarly high classification performance for both oils.

While the thermographic acquisition process inherently captures the temporal evolution of the cooling behaviour, it is important to clarify

how this information is represented in our dataset. The convolutional classifier does not receive explicit temporal data as input: the model operates on individual frames extracted at different instants of the cooling sequence, without timestamps or sequential ordering. Each image encodes the thermal state of the sample at a specific stage of heat dissipation, which allows the network to learn degradation-related features even without an explicit temporal channel. As a result, the learning dynamics observed for both oils are influenced not only by their distinct thermographic behaviour but also by this temporally sampled representation, which was deliberately chosen to preserve the most informative phases of the cooling process while reducing redundancy and computational complexity. This approach has proven sufficient to achieve the robust classification reported for both lubricants.

From a comparative perspective, very similar performance is observed for both oils, with only marginal differences. For engine oil (O-1236), the model achieved slightly higher sensitivity and specificity, which may be explained by greater thermal distribution differences between compliant and non-compliant samples, associated with combustion byproducts and contaminants that significantly affect the oil's thermal conductivity and dissipation capacity [26]. In the case of gearbox oil (O-1178), although differences between compliant and non-compliant samples may be more subtle (as these oils are less exposed to external contaminants and sharp thermal changes), the model was still able to identify degradation-related thermal patterns, with almost identical accuracy.

The comparative analysis is further strengthened by the ROC/AUC results obtained for both lubricants. The fully fine-tuned models exhibit AUC values close to 1.0 for O-1178 and O-1236, confirming near-perfect separability across all decision thresholds. Although the partial fine-tuning configurations show slightly lower AUC values, especially for ResNet-50, their overall ROC profiles remain highly favourable, with consistently high true-positive rates at low false-positive regimes. Importantly, the ROC curves reveal threshold-independent stability that cannot be inferred from confusion matrices or F1-scores alone. This behaviour demonstrates that the discriminative capability of the models is not restricted to a single operating point, but remains robust across the entire decision space, further validating the generalisation ability of the proposed thermographic approach for both lubricant types.

A key element supporting the validity of thermography-based classification is that, unlike optical imaging, thermographic imaging enables the detection of internal changes in the molecular structure and chemical composition of the oil that affect how it absorbs, transmits, and emits infrared radiation. Changes in additive content, the presence of water, oxidation, and metal particles alter the oil's thermal parameters, modifying the thermographic signature of the sample. This information is exploited by the deep neural network to effectively separate states. Therefore, the high sensitivity and specificity achieved by both models reflect not only the quality of the algorithm but also the suitability of IR thermography as an advanced diagnostic technique for lubricating oils [22,27].

Finally, it is worth noting that the model's robustness for both types of lubricants demonstrates the generality of the approach: the method can be applied to various industrial oils as long as the physicochemical changes induced by use perceptibly affect the sample's thermal parameters. IR thermography, combined with artificial intelligence, thus enables effective, objective, and non-invasive monitoring of lubricant condition, with clear benefits for predictive maintenance and operational reliability.

To further reinforce the robustness of the classification results, additional checks were conducted to rule out the possibility of overfitting. The training and validation loss curves obtained for both lubricants show consistent and parallel convergence throughout training, with no divergence between subsets, indicating that the models learned generalizable thermal features rather than memorising the data. This behaviour is fully consistent with the high performance achieved in the validation and test sets, as reflected in the confusion matrices presented

in Sections 3.4 and 3.5. Moreover, the sample-based data separation strategy ensured that all images originating from the same physical oil sample were restricted to a single subset, preventing data leakage and guaranteeing an unbiased estimation of predictive performance. Altogether, these elements support the credibility and statistical soundness of the classification behaviour observed for both lubricant types.

Finally, the combined evidence from confusion matrices, complementary metrics, ROC/AUC analysis, and training stability indicates that the models already operate in a saturated performance regime. In practical terms, this means that alternative architectures such as VGG or MobileNet would not be expected to yield meaningful improvements under the present thermographic conditions. This confirms that ResNet is not only adequate but optimally suited for the classification task addressed in this study.

3.7. Physicochemical foundation from the thermographic perspective

The physicochemical interpretation of the results requires consideration of how lubricant oil degradation and contamination impact their thermal properties and how these changes are detected by infrared thermography. In-service oils undergo a series of processes (oxidation, additive loss, formation of byproducts, contamination with water or metallic particles) that modify parameters such as thermal conductivity, heat capacity, emissivity, and viscosity, all of which are relevant to the sample's thermal behavior [26–28].

The temperature decay during the cooling stage is also strongly dependent on the physicochemical condition of the lubricant. As illustrated in Fig. 9, compliant samples exhibit a progressive and spatially homogeneous attenuation of thermal contrast throughout the cooling sequence, consistent with the smooth, monotonic behaviour expected from conductive heat transfer in a relatively uniform medium [29]. Their viscosity, additive package, and molecular structure allow thermal energy to dissipate uniformly, yielding a gradual and predictable reduction of surface temperature.

In contrast, degraded oils demonstrate markedly different thermal decay dynamics, which are visually evident in the same figure. Oxidation, polymerisation, soot accumulation, fuel dilution, and metallic wear particles modify the oil's internal structure and hinder uniform heat conduction [26]. As a result, non-compliant samples retain sharper thermal gradients for longer periods, show delayed homogenization, and present localised thermal irregularities across the cooling sequence. These effects manifest as non-monotonic decay segments and spatially irregular dissipation patterns, consistent with the presence of micro-heterogeneities and dispersed contaminants that perturb heat-transfer pathways [27].

From a heat-transfer perspective, the expected cooling profile of a high-quality lubricant is governed primarily by Fourier conduction, with minor contributions from natural convection inside the oil column [39]. However, when degradation products accumulate, energy transport becomes more complex, producing local variations in thermal diffusivity and viscosity [26]. These microstructural alterations generate zones that dissipate heat at different rates, producing the vertical thermal gradients and contrast patterns clearly observed in the thermograms across the cooling sequence [8,28]. Consequently, the differences between compliant and non-compliant samples are not only visual but directly rooted in the distinct thermal decay mechanisms arising from their physicochemical condition.

Infrared thermography measures the radiation emitted by the oil surface after being subjected to a controlled thermal stimulus. In new (“compliant”) oils, the thermal response is typically homogeneous, with well-defined patterns reflecting optimal conductivity and emissivity. However, when the oil degrades, the thermogram reveals the appearance of atypical hot or cold zones, irregular patterns of thermal dispersion, or changes in the cooling/heating rate due to alterations in its microstructure and chemical composition [28,30]. For example, the presence of water or solid particles changes the oil's ability to absorb and transmit heat, which translates into detectable variations in the thermographic image [8,26].

Fig. 9. Sequence of thermographic images acquired during the cooling process for the two lubricants (O-1178 and O-1236), comparing compliant (left panels) and non-compliant (right panels) samples. Each panel displays the evolution of the thermal field from the initial temperature (~ 55 °C) to the end of the cooling stage, revealing distinct dissipation patterns associated with the physicochemical condition of each oil. Each rectangular panel corresponds to the frontal surface of the cuvette, which has an internal cross-section of 1 cm \times 4 cm.

For engine oil (O-1236), degradation by oxidation and contamination with soot, water, and combustion byproducts increases thermal heterogeneity, causing thermography to reveal regions with different emissivities and heat dissipation changes. The deep learning model exploits precisely these thermal differences to separate compliant from non-compliant samples. Recent research has shown that contaminant accumulation produces thermal alterations detectable by IR, even before they become evident through conventional visual means or chemical analysis [27–29].

For gearbox oil (O-1178), although degradation processes are usually less drastic than in engine oil, the formation of metallic particles and oxidation products from friction and high temperatures also induces changes in the thermal response, especially in surface temperature distribution and in the appearance of “thermal islands” in the IR image. IR thermography has been successfully used to monitor the condition of industrial gear oils, detecting incipient failures through subtle variations in thermal response before catastrophic failure occurs [26,30].

From a physicochemical perspective, changes in thermal patterns can be correlated with the deterioration of key oil properties: decreased viscosity, increased acid number, increased contaminants, and reduced antioxidant and anti-wear additives [28]. By affecting conductivity and heat capacity, these processes modify heat propagation following a thermal pulse, which is reflected as detectable differences in the IR image [27,29].

The combined use of infrared thermography and deep learning not only enables automation and objectivity in diagnosis but also provides an extremely sensitive tool, capable of detecting incipient deterioration not visible to the naked eye or detectable through traditional inspections. Thus, the methodology employed in this study aligns with the current trend in predictive lubricant monitoring, where thermography is emerging as a cutting-edge technology due to its speed, non-invasive analysis capabilities, and sensitivity to subtle physicochemical changes [8,9,22,27].

In the present work, the results reinforce this foundation, as a significant correspondence was observed between the most relevant regions identified by Grad-CAM heatmaps and the physicochemical parameters measured in the laboratory. Consistently, the areas of thermographic images considered critical for classification by the model tend to coincide with those where analyses show higher levels of degradation, such as increased acidity, presence of metallic particles, or higher contaminant levels [26,27,29]. This correspondence, observed in both types of oils evaluated, provides robust evidence that the deep learning model not only detects visual patterns but also genuinely captures thermal indicators linked to lubricant composition and chemical state. Thus, the integration of explanatory techniques such as Grad-CAM enables a direct link between information extracted through artificial intelligence and the classical physicochemical foundations of oil diagnostics [8,22,23].

Compared to conventional online sensors, such as viscosity or near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopic probes, or indirect monitoring approaches like vibration analysis, our method demonstrates higher sensitivity and specificity for detecting lubricant degradation, while also enabling rapid, non-contact measurements with reduced operational complexity. These advantages underscore its potential as a practical diagnostic tool for both field and laboratory environments [22,27,29].

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of combining infrared thermography with deep convolutional neural networks for the automatic assessment of lubricating oil condition in critical applications, both civil and military. By analyzing more than 10,000 thermographic images corresponding to two logistically significant industrial oils (O-1178, gearbox oil, and O-1236, engine oil), we validated an autonomous and non-destructive diagnostic system capable of accurately discriminating between “compliant” and “non-compliant”

samples.

One of the main achievements of this work lies in obtaining an almost perfect binary classification based on the thermal signatures of oils during controlled cooling processes. The ResNet-34 and ResNet-50 models, selected after comparing various state-of-the-art computer vision architectures, showed outstanding performance, particularly when full fine-tuning of all parameters was allowed. Notably, ResNet-34 proved to be the most reliable option, achieving 100 % sensitivity and specificity in the detection of non-compliant samples for both types of lubricant, thus eliminating the risk of false negatives. This is essential in predictive maintenance applications where safety and operational availability depend on early failure detection.

The thermographic image-based approach, unlike conventional laboratory methods, enables rapid, objective, and non-invasive inspection of large sample volumes without the need for prior preparation or oil extraction. The high homogeneity and quality of the images used, confirmed by gradient distribution and Grad-CAM heatmap interpretation, further reinforce the robustness and explainability of the developed models. The neural network was able to identify micro-thermal patterns associated with physicochemical degradation processes such as oxidation, contamination with water or metallic particles, and additive depletion, all of which have direct relevance to equipment performance and service life.

In addition to improving operational availability by avoiding unnecessary oil changes and enabling anticipation of the real end-of-life of lubricants, the proposed methodology also has a positive environmental impact. Optimizing maintenance intervals through precise diagnostics contributes to reducing hazardous waste and resource consumption, in line with sustainability and circular economy objectives.

In addition, the ROC/AUC analysis confirmed the stability of the models across all decision thresholds, with fully fine-tuned architectures achieving AUC values close to 1.0 and no false negatives in the critical non-compliant class. This threshold-independent robustness, combined with the consistency observed across complementary metrics such as F1-score and training-validation convergence, indicates that the classifiers operate within a saturated performance regime. Accordingly, the proposed ResNet-based framework achieves the highest level of discriminative reliability that can be expected under the present thermographic conditions.

Finally, the generality of the method has been demonstrated by its success with two oils exhibiting different degradation mechanisms, suggesting applicability to a wide range of industrial lubricants. The system can be transferred and adapted to other operational settings, provided that experimental conditions are reproduced and representative thermographic data on oil degradation are available. Nevertheless, it is important to note that if experimental conditions change significantly (e.g., substantial variations in operating temperature, container type, or oil composition), recalibration or retraining of the model will be required to ensure diagnostic reliability, as optimal performance depends on the similarity between training and application conditions.

This study introduces a novel framework for intelligent predictive maintenance of lubricating oils, demonstrating that the integration of infrared thermography and deep learning effectively addresses the limitations of conventional diagnostic methods by providing rapid, objective, sensitive, and interpretable results. Looking ahead, the methodology holds promise for application to a broader range of lubricant types, as well as for integration into online monitoring systems and continuous optimisation through training on larger, more diverse datasets.

Nonetheless, to fully validate the approach, additional research is needed to assess its performance with oils of different chemical compositions, under varying operational stresses, and in real-world environments characterized by greater variability. Current and future efforts are directed toward expanding the dataset, to enhance its robustness and practical utility.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alicia Ortiz-Chiliquinga: Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Fernando Moreno-Haya:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Investigation. **Carlos López-Pingarrón:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Carlos Jesús Vega-Vera:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **José S. Torrecilla:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The manuscript entitled "*Infrared Thermography Coupled with Deep Learning for Fast and Reliable Predictive Monitoring of Lubricating Oils in Dual-Use Heavy-Duty Vehicles*" is original, currently unpublished, and not under consideration for publication elsewhere.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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